

Optimization Model of an Innovative Automated Warehouse featuring Climbing Collaborative Robots

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A Complete MILP formulation

A.1 Sets

- P : Set of pickers
- K : Set of robots
- B : Set of boxes
- G : Set of garment types
- S : Set of garment sizes
- O : Set of customer orders
- $M = \{1, \dots, M_n\}$: Set of possible missions for each box. Each box can be used in multiple missions
- $V^{ch} = \{1, \dots, MAX_CH_MISSIONS\}$: Possible charging visits per robot
- $C = \{1, \dots, Xslots\}$: Charging station slots
- N : Set of nodes: $N = \{START, END\} \cup N^{PU} \cup N^V \cup N^{RT} \cup N^{CH}$
- $START$: Start node of a robot route
- END : End node of a robot route
- $PU(b, m)$: Represents the pickup of box $b \in B$ for mission $m \in M$
- $V(p, b, m)$: Represents a visit of picker $p \in P$ by box $b \in B$ during mission $m \in M$
- $RT(b, m)$: Represents the return of box $b \in B$ to its storage location at the end of mission $m \in M$
- $CH(v)$: Represents the v -th possible charging operation of a robot

A.2 Parameters

Demand and inventory parameters

- $dem_{o,g,s}$: Demand for order $o \in O$ for garment type $g \in G$ and size $s \in S$
- $gOfBox_b$: garment type stored in box $b \in B$
- $q_{b,s}$: Initial stock of box $b \in B$ for size $s \in S$

Spatial Parameters

- $xShelf_b, yShelf_b, zShelf_b$: Coordinates of the shelf containing box $b \in B$
- $xPick_p, yPick_p$: Coordinates of picker $p \in P$
- $xCharge, yCharge$: Coordinates of the charging station
- $xStart_k, yStart_k$: Coordinates of the initial position of robot $k \in K$
- $xRefill, yRefill$: Coordinates of the refill station
- $distShelfPick_{b,p}$: Travel distance between the storage location of box $b \in B$ and picker station $p \in P$. Represents the travel required when a robot transports a box from its shelf to a picker.
- $distStartShelf_{k,b}$: Travel distance between the initial position of robot $k \in K$ and the shelf containing box $b \in B$. Determines the travel required for the first pickup operation of a robot route.
- $distPickPick_{p_1,p_2}$: Travel distance between picker stations $p_1, p_2 \in P$. This parameter allows the model to account for travel between pickers when the same box serves multiple pickers.
- $distShelfShelf_{b_1,b_2}$: Travel distance between the shelves of boxes $b_1, b_2 \in B$. This parameter models transitions between missions involving different boxes.
- $distRefillShelf_b$: Travel distance between the shelf of box $b \in B$ and the refill station. This distance is assumed to be symmetric (shelf - refill and refill - shelf).
- $distStartCharge_k$: Travel distance between the initial location of robot $k \in K$ and the charging station. This parameter allows a robot to visit the charging station immediately after starting its route if necessary.
- $distShelfCharge_b$: Travel distance between the shelf location of box $b \in B$ and the charging station. This distance is used when a robot finishes a mission and moves to the charging station.
- $distChargeShelf_b$: Travel distance between the charging station and the shelf of box $b \in B$. This parameter models the travel from a charging operation to the next pickup.

Time Parameters

- v^{XY} : Travel time per unit planar distance.
- $tHook, tUnhook, tGrab$: Manipulation times at shelf level.
- $tDrop, tPickup$: Box drop and pickup times at pickers.
- $\alpha^{up}, \alpha^{down}$: Vertical movement coefficients.
- $tPickSetup_p$: Setup time at picker $p \in P$.
- $tPickUnit_p$: Picking time per item at picker $p \in P$.

- $tCharge$: Charging duration.
- $tRefill$: Refill service time.
- $Wbuffer$: Maximum waiting time for arrival of box to picker start.

Energy Parameters

- B_{max} : Robot battery capacity.
- e^{XY} : Energy consumption per unit of distance.
- $eHook, eUnHook, eGrab$: Manipulation energy costs.
- $eDrop, ePickup$: Picker interaction energy costs.
- β^{up}, β^{down} : Vertical motion coefficients.
- $eRefill$: Refill energy cost

Big-M Parameters

- $Mtime$: large constant used in time propagation constraints.
- $Mbat$: large constant used in battery propagation constraints.

A.3 Decision Variables

Order Assignment

- $x_{p,o} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if order $o \in O$ is assigned to picker $p \in P$, 0 otherwise.

Item allocation and mission activation

- $a_{p,b,m,s} \in \mathbb{Z}_+$: Number of items of size $s \in S$ picked by picker $p \in P$ from box $b \in B$ in mission $m \in M$.
- $y_{p,b,m} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if mission $m \in M$ of box $b \in B$ visits picker $p \in P$, 0 otherwise.
- $usedM_{b,m} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if mission $m \in M$ of box $b \in B$ is active, 0 otherwise.
- $usedBox_b \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if box $b \in B$ is used, 0 otherwise.
- $refillBefore_{b,m} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if a refill of box $b \in B$ is performed before mission $m \in M$, 0 otherwise.
- $refillCount_b \in \mathbb{Z}_+$: Number of refill cycles associated with box $b \in B$.
- $stockStart_{b,m,s} \in \mathbb{Z}_+$: Stock available at start of mission $m \in M$
- $stockEnd_{b,m,s} \in \mathbb{Z}_+$: Stock remaining after mission $m \in M$

Picker timing and task sequencing

- $tArr_{p,b,m} \geq 0$: Arrival time of mission $m \in M$ of box $b \in B$ at picker $p \in P$.
- $tP_{p,b,m} \geq 0$: Start time of service of mission $m \in M$ of box $b \in B$ at picker $p \in P$.
- $\pi_{p,b_1,m_1,b_2,m_2} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if task (b_1, m_1) is performed before task (b_2, m_2) on picker $p \in P$. ($b_1, b_2 \in B; m_1, m_2 \in M; b_1, m_1 \neq b_2, m_2$), 0 otherwise.

Robot assignment

- $rb_{k,b} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if robot $k \in K$ is assigned to box $b \in B$, 0 otherwise.
- $useRobot_k \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if robot $k \in K$ is used, 0 otherwise.

Routing variables

- $arc_{k,i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if robot $k \in K$ uses arc (i, j) , 0 otherwise.
- $activeN_{k,n} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if node $n \in N$ is active in the route of robot $k \in K$, 0 otherwise.
- $tNode_{k,n} \geq 0$: Time at which robot $k \in K$ reaches node $n \in N$.
- $Ebefore_{k,n} \geq 0$; $Eafter_{k,n} \geq 0$: Battery level of robot $k \in K$ before and after node $n \in N$.

Charging variables

- $doCharge_{k,v} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if robot $k \in K$ performs a charging visit $v \in V^{ch}$, 0 otherwise.
- $zSlot_{k,v,c} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if charging visit $v \in V^{ch}$ of robot $k \in K$ is assigned to slot $c \in C$, 0 otherwise.
- $tCh_{k,v} \geq 0$: Start time of charging visit $v \in V^{ch}$ of robot $k \in K$.
- $nCharge_k \in \mathbb{Z}_+$: Number of charging visits performed by robot $k \in K$.
- $oc_{c,k_1,v_1,k_2,v_2} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if charging visit $v_1 \in V^{ch}$ of robot $k_1 \in K$ is scheduled before charging visit $v_2 \in V^{ch}$ of robot $k_2 \in K$ on slot $c \in C$, 0 otherwise.

Makespan variables

- $C_{max} \geq 0$: Represents the system makespan.
- $C_{robot_k} \geq 0$: Represents the completion time of robot $k \in K$.

Derived expressions

Travel times are obtained from the corresponding distances as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
TShelfPick_{b,p} &= v^{XY} \cdot distShelfPick_{b,p} \quad \forall b \in B, p \in P \\
TStartShelf_{k,b} &= v^{XY} \cdot distStartShelf_{k,b} \quad \forall k \in K, b \in B \\
TPickPick_{p_1,p_2} &= v^{XY} \cdot distPickPick_{p_1,p_2} \quad \forall p_1, p_2 \in P \\
TShelfShelf_{b_1,b_2} &= v^{XY} \cdot distShelfShelf_{b_1,b_2} \quad \forall b_1, b_2 \in B \\
TRefillShelf_b &= v^{XY} \cdot distRefillShelf_b \quad \forall b \in B \\
TShelfCharge_b &= v^{XY} \cdot distShelfCharge_b \quad \forall b \in B \\
TChargeShelf_b &= v^{XY} \cdot distChargeShelf_b \quad \forall b \in B \\
TStartCharge_k &= v^{XY} \cdot distStartCharge_k \quad \forall k \in K
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Energy consumption is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 EShelfPick_{b,p} &= e^{XY} \cdot distShelfPick_{b,p} \quad \forall b \in B, p \in P \\
 EStartShelf_{k,b} &= e^{XY} \cdot distStartShelf_{k,b} \quad \forall k \in K, b \in B \\
 EPickPick_{p_1,p_2} &= e^{XY} \cdot distPickPick_{p_1,p_2} \quad \forall p_1, p_2 \in P \\
 EShelfShelf_{b_1,b_2} &= e^{XY} \cdot distShelfShelf_{b_1,b_2} \quad \forall b_1, b_2 \in B \\
 ERefillShelf_b &= e^{XY} \cdot distRefillShelf_b \quad \forall b \in B \\
 EShelfCharge_b &= e^{XY} \cdot distShelfCharge_b \quad \forall b \in B \\
 EChargeShelf_b &= e^{XY} \cdot distChargeShelf_b \quad \forall b \in B \\
 EStartCharge_k &= e^{XY} \cdot distStartCharge_k \quad \forall k \in K
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Shelf service time and energy for box $b \in B$ are:

$$T_b^{climb} = tHook + \alpha^{up} zShelf_b + tGrab + \alpha^{down} zShelf_b + tUnhook \tag{3}$$

$$E_b^{climb} = eHook + \beta^{up} zShelf_b + eGrab + \beta^{down} zShelf_b + eUnhook \tag{4}$$

The refill cycle is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_b^{refillCycle} &= 2TRefillShelf_b + tRefill \quad \forall b \in B \\
 E_b^{refillCycle} &= 2ERefillShelf_b + eRefill \quad \forall b \in B
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The processing time of a picker is:

$$pickerTime_{p,b,m} = tPickSetup_p \cdot y_{p,b,m} + tPickUnit_p \sum_{s \in S} a_{p,b,m,s} \quad \forall p, b, m \tag{6}$$

Let $b(n), m(n)$ and $p(n)$ denote the box, mission and picker associated with node $n \in N$. The duration of service of a routing node $n \in N$ is defined by the node type:

$$dur_n = \begin{cases} 0, & n = START \text{ or } n = END \\ T_b^{climb} + T_b^{refillCycle} refillBefore_{b,m}, & n = PU(b, m) \\ tDrop + (tP_{p,b,m} - tArr_{p,b,m}) + pickerTime_{p,b,m} + tPickup, & n = V(p, b, m) \\ T_b^{climb}, & n = RT(b, m) \\ tCharge, & n = CH(v) \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Similarly, the service energy consumption at node $n \in N$ is:

$$e_n = \begin{cases} 0, & n = START \text{ or } n = END \\ E_b^{climb} + E_b^{refillCycle} refillBefore_{b,m}, & n = PU(b, m) \\ eDrop + ePickup, & n = V(p, b, m) \\ E_b^{climb}, & n = RT(b, m) \\ 0, & n = CH(v) \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

A.4 Objective Function

The objective (9) is to minimize the system makespan (first term), penalize unnecessary battery recharges (second term), and to shift to the left temporal feasible schedules (third term):

$$\begin{aligned} & \min C_{max} + \\ & + \lambda_1 \sum_{k \in K} nCharge_k + \\ & + \lambda_2 \left(\sum_{k \in K} \sum_{n \in N} tNode_{k,n} + \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M} tP_{p,b,m} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\lambda_1 \ll 1$ and $\lambda_2 \ll \lambda_1$.

A.5 Constraints

For readability, constraints are grouped according to their operational role. **Order assignment**

Each order must be assigned to exactly one picker (10):

$$\sum_{p \in P} x_{p,o} = 1 \quad \forall o \in O \quad (10)$$

For each picker, garment type, and size, the total quantity allocated from boxes must exactly satisfy the demand of the orders assigned to that picker (11):

$$\sum_{\substack{b \in B \\ g \text{ of } Box = g}} \sum_{m \in M} a_{p,b,m,s} = \sum_{o \in O} dem_{o,g,s} x_{p,o} \quad \forall p \in P, g \in G, s \in S \quad (11)$$

Missions, stock evolution and refill

The first mission of each box starts with initial stock and no refill (12–13):

$$refillBefore_{b,1} = 0 \quad \forall b \in B \quad (12)$$

$$stockStart_{b,1,s} = q_{b,s} \cdot usedM_{b,1} \quad \forall b \in B, s \in S \quad (13)$$

The total quantity picked in a mission cannot exceed the available stock (14):

$$\sum_{p \in P} a_{p,b,m,s} \leq stockStart_{b,m,s} \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M, s \in S \quad (14)$$

The remaining stock after each mission is updated as follows (15):

$$stockEnd_{b,m,s} = stockStart_{b,m,s} - \sum_{p \in P} a_{p,b,m,s} \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M, s \in S \quad (15)$$

For subsequent missions, the available stock depends on whether there is a refill or not (16–19):

$$\begin{aligned} stockStart_{b,m,s} &\leq stockEnd_{b,m-1,s} + q_{b,s} \cdot refillBefore_{b,m} \\ &\forall b \in B, m = 2, \dots, M_n, \forall s \in S \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} stockStart_{b,m,s} &\geq stockEnd_{b,m-1,s} - q_{b,s} \cdot refillBefore_{b,m} \\ &\forall b \in B, m = 2, \dots, M_n, \forall s \in S \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} stockStart_{b,m,s} &\leq q_{b,s} + q_{b,s}(1 - refillBefore_{b,m}) \\ &\forall b \in B, m = 2, \dots, M_n, \forall s \in S \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} stockStart_{b,m,s} &\geq q_{b,s} - q_{b,s}(1 - refillBefore_{b,m}) \\ &\forall b \in B, m = 2, \dots, M_n, \forall s \in S \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Refill can only be activated if both consecutive missions exist (20):

$$\begin{aligned} refillBefore_{b,m} &\leq usedM_{b,m} \\ refillBefore_{b,m} &\leq usedM_{b,m-1} \\ &\forall b \in B, m \geq 2 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The total number of refill operations associated with each box is computed as follows (21):

$$refillCount_b = \sum_{m=2}^{M_n} refillBefore_{b,m} \quad \forall b \in B \quad (21)$$

Stock variables are forced to zero when the corresponding mission is inactive (22):

$$\begin{aligned} stockStart_{b,m,s} &\leq q_{b,s} \cdot usedM_{b,m}, & stockEnd_{b,m,s} &\leq q_{b,s} \cdot usedM_{b,m} \\ && &\forall b \in B, m \in M, s \in S \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The picked quantities are linked to visit decisions (23):

$$a_{p,b,m,s} \leq q_{b,s} \cdot y_{p,b,m} \quad \forall p, b, m, s \quad (23)$$

If a visit occurs, at least one item must be picked (24):

$$\sum_{s \in S} a_{p,b,m,s} \geq y_{p,b,m} \quad \forall p, b, m \quad (24)$$

Each active mission must include at least one picker visit (25):

$$\sum_{p \in P} y_{p,b,m} \geq usedM_{b,m} \quad \forall b, m \quad (25)$$

Picker visits can only occur in active missions (26):

$$y_{p,b,m} \leq usedM_{b,m} \quad \forall p, b, m \quad (26)$$

Box activation is linked to mission usage (27–28):

$$usedBox_b \leq \sum_{m \in M} usedM_{b,m} \quad (27)$$

$$\sum_{m \in M} usedM_{b,m} \leq M_n \cdot usedBox_b \quad (28)$$

Missions are activated consecutively (29):

$$usedM_{b,m} \geq usedM_{b,m+1} \quad \forall b \in B, m = 1, \dots, M_n - 1 \quad (29)$$

Robot assignment

Each used box is assigned to exactly one robot (30):

$$\sum_{k \in K} rb_{k,b} = usedBox_b \quad \forall b \in B \quad (30)$$

Robot activation is consistent with assigned boxes (31):

$$\sum_{b \in B} rb_{k,b} \leq |B| \cdot useRobot_k, \quad \sum_{b \in B} rb_{k,b} \geq useRobot_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad (31)$$

Charging activation

If charging is enabled, each charging visit must be assigned to exactly one charging slot (32):

$$\sum_{c \in C} zSlot_{k,v,c} = doCharge_{k,v} \quad \forall k \in K, v \in V^{ch} \quad (32)$$

The total number of charging visits performed by each robot is computed as (33):

$$nCharge_k = \sum_{v \in V^{ch}} doCharge_{k,v} \quad \forall k \in K \quad (33)$$

The number of charging visits is bounded by the maximum allowed number (34):

$$nCharge_k \leq MAX_CH_MISSIONS \quad \forall k \in K \quad (34)$$

Charging visits are activated consecutively (35):

$$doCharge_{k,v} \leq doCharge_{k,v-1} \quad \forall k \in K, v = 2, \dots, MAX_CH_MISSIONS \quad (35)$$

Active nodes

The start and end nodes are active if and only if the robot is used (36):

$$activeN_{k,START} = useRobot_k, \quad activeN_{k,END} = useRobot_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad (36)$$

Pickup nodes are active if the corresponding mission is active and the robot is assigned to the box (37):

$$\begin{aligned}
activeN_{k,PU(b,m)} &\leq rb_{k,b} \\
activeN_{k,PU(b,m)} &\leq usedM_{b,m} \\
activeN_{k,PU(b,m)} &\geq rb_{k,b} + usedM_{b,m} - 1 \\
&\forall k \in K, b \in B, m \in M
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Return nodes are active if the corresponding mission is active and the robot is assigned to the box (38):

$$\begin{aligned}
activeN_{k,RT(b,m)} &\leq rb_{k,b} \\
activeN_{k,RT(b,m)} &\leq usedM_{b,m} \\
activeN_{k,RT(b,m)} &\geq rb_{k,b} + usedM_{b,m} - 1 \\
&\forall k \in K, b \in B, m \in M
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

Visit nodes are active if and only if the robot handles the box and the visit is selected (39):

$$\begin{aligned}
activeN_{k,V(p,b,m)} &\leq rb_{k,b} \\
activeN_{k,V(p,b,m)} &\leq y_{p,b,m} \\
activeN_{k,V(p,b,m)} &\geq rb_{k,b} + y_{p,b,m} - 1 \\
&\forall k \in K, p \in P, b \in B, m \in M
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

Charging nodes are active if the corresponding charging visit is used (40):

$$activeN_{k,CH(v)} = doCharge_{k,v} \quad \forall k \in K, v \in V^{ch} \tag{40}$$

Routing constraints

Self-loops are not allowed (41):

$$arc_{k,i,i} = 0 \quad \forall k \in K, i \in N \tag{41}$$

Flow conservation ensures a valid route for each robot (42)–(43):

$$\sum_{\substack{i \in N \\ i \neq n}} arc_{k,i,n} = activeN_{k,n} \quad \forall k \in K, n \in N \setminus \{START, END\} \tag{42}$$

$$\sum_{\substack{j \in N \\ j \neq n}} arc_{k,n,j} = activeN_{k,n} \quad \forall k \in K, n \in N \setminus \{START, END\} \tag{43}$$

The route starts and ends correctly (44–47):

$$\sum_{\substack{j \in N \\ j \neq START}} arc_{k,START,j} = useRobot_k \quad \forall k \in K \tag{44}$$

$$\sum_{\substack{i \in N \\ i \neq END}} arc_{k,i,END} = useRobot_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad (45)$$

$$\sum_{i \in N} arc_{k,i,START} = 0 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (46)$$

$$\sum_{j \in N} arc_{k,END,j} = 0 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (47)$$

For every robot $k \in K$, binary variable $arc_{k,i,j}$ is forced to 0 whenever the transition (i, j) is not possible according to the mission logic.

Time constraints

The route of each robot starts at time zero (48):

$$tNode_{k,START} = 0 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (48)$$

Time propagation along arcs is enforced by (49):

$$tNode_{k,j} \geq tNode_{k,i} + dur_i + travelT_{k,i,j} - Mtime(1 - arc_{k,i,j}) \quad \forall k \in K, \forall i, j \in N : i \neq j \quad (49)$$

Arrival times of picker visits

The arrival time of a box at a picker is linked to the time of the corresponding active visit node (50–52):

$$tArr_{p,b,m} \geq 0 \quad \forall p \in P, b \in B, m \in M \quad (50)$$

$$tArr_{p,b,m} \leq Mtime \cdot y_{p,b,m} \quad \forall p \in P, b \in B, m \in M \quad (51)$$

$$\begin{aligned} tArr_{p,b,m} &\geq tNode_{k,V(p,b,m)} - Mtime(1 - activeN_{k,V(p,b,m)}) \\ tArr_{p,b,m} &\leq tNode_{k,V(p,b,m)} + Mtime(1 - activeN_{k,V(p,b,m)}) \end{aligned} \quad \forall p \in P, b \in B, m \in M, k \in K \quad (52)$$

Picker scheduling

Picking can only start after box arrival and within the allowed waiting buffer (53–55):

$$tP_{p,b,m} \geq tArr_{p,b,m} - Mtime(1 - y_{p,b,m}) \quad \forall p \in P, b \in B, m \in M \quad (53)$$

$$tP_{p,b,m} \leq tArr_{p,b,m} + Wbuffer + Mtime(1 - y_{p,b,m}) \quad \forall p \in P, b \in B, m \in M \quad (54)$$

$$tP_{p,b,m} \leq Mtime \cdot y_{p,b,m} \quad \forall p \in P, b \in B, m \in M \quad (55)$$

If two tasks are assigned to the same picker, one of them must precede the other (56–58):

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{p,b_1,m_1,b_2,m_2} &\leq y_{p,b_1,m_1}, \quad \pi_{p,b_1,m_1,b_2,m_2} \leq y_{p,b_2,m_2} \\ &\forall p \in P, \forall b_1, b_2 \in B, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{p,b_1,m_1,b_2,m_2} + \pi_{p,b_2,m_2,b_1,m_1} &\geq y_{p,b_1,m_1} + y_{p,b_2,m_2} - 1 \\ \forall p \in P, \forall b_1, b_2 \in B, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

$$\begin{aligned} tP_{p,b_2,m_2} &\geq tP_{p,b_1,m_1} + pickerTime_{p,b_1,m_1} - Mtime(1 - \pi_{p,b_1,m_1,b_2,m_2}) \\ \forall p \in P, \forall b_1, b_2 \in B, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

Charging timing and charging-slot conflicts

The start time of a charging operation is linked to the corresponding charging node (59):

$$\begin{aligned} tCh_{k,v} &\geq tNode_{k,CH(v)} - Mtime(1 - doCharge_{k,v}) \\ tCh_{k,v} &\leq tNode_{k,CH(v)} + Mtime(1 - doCharge_{k,v}) \\ \forall k \in K, v \in V^{ch} \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

If two charging visits use the same slot, they must be temporally ordered and cannot overlap (60):

$$\begin{aligned} tCh_{k_2,v_2} &\geq tCh_{k_1,v_1} + tCharge - \\ &- Mtime\left(3 - zSlot_{k_1,v_1,c} - zSlot_{k_2,v_2,c} - oc_{c,k_1,v_1,k_2,v_2}\right) \\ \forall c \in C, \forall k_1, k_2 \in K, \forall v_1, v_2 \in V^{ch} \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

Battery constraints

Each robot starts with a full battery (61):

$$Ebefore_{k,START} = B_{max}, \quad Eafter_{k,START} = B_{max} \quad \forall k \in K \quad (61)$$

For non-charging nodes, the battery level after service is reduced by the node service energy (63):

$$Eafter_{k,n} \leq Ebefore_{k,n} - eNode_n + Mbat(1 - activeN_{k,n}) \quad (62)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Eafter_{k,n} &\geq Ebefore_{k,n} - eNode_n - Mbat(1 - activeN_{k,n}) \\ \forall k \in K, n \in N : n \neq START, END, nType(n) \neq CH \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

At charging nodes, the battery is restored to full capacity (64):

$$\begin{aligned} Eafter_{k,n} &\geq B_{max} - Mbat(1 - activeN_{k,n}) \\ Eafter_{k,n} &\leq B_{max} + Mbat(1 - activeN_{k,n}) \\ \forall k \in K, n \in N : nType(n) = CH \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

Battery consumption along travel arcs is enforced by (66):

$$Ebefore_{k,j} \leq Eafter_{k,i} - travelE_{k,i,j} + Mbat(1 - arc_{k,i,j}) \quad (65)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Ebefore_{k,j} &\geq Eafter_{k,i} - travelE_{k,i,j} - Mbat(1 - arc_{k,i,j}) \\ \forall k \in K, i, j \in N : i \neq j \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

Battery levels are bounded at all nodes (67):

$$0 \leq Ebefore_{k,n} \leq B_{max}, \quad 0 \leq Eafter_{k,n} \leq B_{max} \quad \forall k \in K, n \in N \quad (67)$$

At the end node, the battery level remains unchanged (68):

$$Eafter_{k,END} = Ebefore_{k,END} \quad \forall k \in K \quad (68)$$

Mission ordering for the same box

If mission $m + 1$ is used, its pickup cannot occur before the pickup of mission m (69):

$$\begin{aligned} tNode_{k,PU(b,m+1)} &\geq tNode_{k,PU(b,m)} - \\ &- Mtime \left(2 - activeN_{k,PU(b,m)} - activeN_{k,PU(b,m+1)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

$$\forall b \in B, m = 1, \dots, M_n - 1, k \in K$$

Robot completion time and makespan

The completion time of each robot is linked to the last serviced node before the end node (70–71):

$$\begin{aligned} Crobot_k &\geq tNode_{k,i} + dur_i - Mtime(1 - arc_{k,i,END}) \\ &\forall k \in K, i \in N : i \neq END \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Crobot_k &\leq tNode_{k,i} + dur_i + Mtime(1 - arc_{k,i,END}) \\ &\forall k \in K, i \in N : i \neq END \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

The overall makespan is defined as the maximum robot completion time (72):

$$C_{max} \geq Crobot_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad (72)$$

Unused robots must have zero completion time (73):

$$Crobot_k \leq Mtime \cdot useRobot_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad (73)$$

Robot symmetry breaking

To reduce symmetric solutions, robots are ordered according to their activation (74):

$$useRobot_k \geq useRobot_{k+1} \quad \forall k = 1, \dots, |K| - 1 \quad (74)$$

The number of active nodes is also ordered (75):

$$\sum_{n \in N} activeN_{k,n} \geq \sum_{n \in N} activeN_{k+1,n} \quad \forall k = 1, \dots, |K| - 1 \quad (75)$$

Finally, end times are ordered (76):

$$\begin{aligned} tNode_{k,END} &\leq tNode_{k+1,END} + Mtime(1 - useRobot_{k+1}) \\ &\forall k = 1, \dots, |K| - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$